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1 Introduction

This is the data documentation document for the paper: **Curd Schade and Ruud Egging-Bratseth. *Battery degradation: impact on economic dispatch.* (In review)**, for which the preprint is available at: <https://doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.21253068.v1>

In the paper, we implement three types of degradation. To reflect the nonlinearity of two of the three degradation functions, we use piecewise linear functions.

The three types of degradation (also *aging* or, *stress*) we represent are (driven by):

- Cycle Depth (CD), presented in sections 3.2 and 4.2.1 in the paper.
 - Sixteen evenly spaced virtual SOC battery segments.
- Average cycle State of Charge (SOC), presented in section 4.2.2 in the paper.
 - No interpolation.
- SOC-based calendar aging (CAL), presented in sections 3.1 and 4.2.3 in the paper.
 - Four SOC segments defined by five breakpoints at 0%, 30%, 60%, 70% and 100% SOC.

Data sources with reference numbers according to the references in the paper.

- [7] Keil et al. *Calendar Aging of Lithium-Ion Batteries*. J of The Electrochemical Society 2016;163(9):A1872– A1880.
- [16] Laresgoiti et al. *Modeling mechanical degradation in lithium ion batteries during cycling: Solid electrolyte interphase fracture*. J of Power Sources 2015 12;300:112–122.
- [37] Bundesnetzagentur, Marktdaten; 2019. <https://www.smard.de/home/downloadcenter>
- [38] electricity price; 2019. <https://strom-report.de/strompreise/#strompreiszusammensetzung>
- [40] Mauler et al. *Battery cost forecasting: a review of methods and results with an outlook to 2050*. Energy & Environmental Science 2021.

Three data sources not mentioned (explicitly) in the paper:

- [A] Pod Point <https://pod-point.com/guides/driver/how-long-to-charge-an-electric-car>
- [B] Tesla https://digitalassets.tesla.com/tesla-contents/image/upload/powerwall-plus-datasheet-na-en_001
- [C] Mobility House https://www.mobilityhouse.com/int_en/knowledge-center/article/charging-time-summary

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Table 1. Parameters, data values, sources and comments.

Par.	Description	Used in	Value	Unit	Source	Page nr.	Comment
a^{CD}	Capacity loss for maximum cycle depth	CD aging	0.04519	%/cycle	[16]	121	Estimated from based data series from [16].
c^{MAX}	Maximum charge rate	Battery model	60	kW	Various		$0.6 \times 100 kWh = 60 kWh$. The maximum C-rate, or power to energy ratio, is 0.6. This value is in the range of values for fast charging electric car batteries presented by electric vehicle charging provider Pod Point [A]. For reference, Tesla [B] Power wall (5kW/13.5kwh = almost 0.4)
d^{MAX}	Maximum discharge rate	Battery model	60	kW	Various		The same as c^{MAX}
e^{RAT}	Rated energy capacity of battery	Battery model	100	kWh	Various		Several upscale electric cars (Mercedes EQS, BMWi7, Tesla X 100D) have batteries of around 100 kWh. EV charging service provider Mobility House. [C]
f	Fitting parameter average SOC stress	SOC aging	0.0085	% / cycle	[16]	121	Estimated based on [16]. In contrast to [16], we disregard the positive constant (<i>the function value at 50% SOC</i>) as it is CD damage and we reflect this mechanism separately in our paper. We scale the value by the maximum deviation of 50%.
m	Fatigue strength exponent	CD aging	0.4926		[16]	121	Estimated based data series from [16] (c.f., Fig. 1).
o_i^{CAL}	Calendar aging breakpoint value	CAL aging	Tab 3 in paper; Table 3 below	% / hour	[7]	A1874	Decide segments and scale data from [7]. Details in Section 1.1 below.
o_j^{CD}	SOC breakpoint value	CD aging	See separate table.		Self-defined		Virtual battery segments. 17 evenly spaced breakpoints provide a very granular representation. Used in Equation (2) in the paper, while stress values are computed by using equation (1).
p_h	Electricity price (hourly)	Sales model	See separate table	€ / kWh	[37],[38]		We consider a two-day period, 22 – 24 April, 2am-2am, in 2019 hourly German spot prices [37], to which we add a grid fee of 7.39 ct [38] and 19% value-added tax. Any negative hourly prices based on this are replaced by the value 0.1 ct/kWh
r	Replacement cost battery	Battery model	150	€ / kWh	[40]		The range from 50 to 500 € /kWh captures uncertainty in battery price forecasts [40] as well as (installation) cost differences for different battery pack sizes.

Par.	Description	Used in	Value	Unit	Source	Page nr.	Comment
v^D	Charging efficiency	Battery model	95	%			Based on 90% round-trip efficiency Tesla [B] Powerwall
v^D	Discharging efficiency	Battery model	95	%			Based on 90% round-trip efficiency Tesla [B] Powerwall;
y_i	Calendar aging breakpoint aging value	CAL	Table 3 in the paper, or Table 3 below				Decide segments and scale data from [7]. Details in Section 1.1 below.

1.1 Calendar aging breakpoint values

Source: Graph in [7] with values, using a visual recognition tool: <https://apps.automeris.io/wpd/>.

- Visual recognition (SOC and relative capacity after ten months) from the ten-month NMC data at 25°C in [7], in the first two columns of Table 2.
- The third column is 100% minus value in the second column.
- We compute hourly degradation values from: “Q_loss hourly”, in the fourth column.

Extrapolating these values lineary results in an annual degradation at full SOC of 7.83% (bottom of the fifth column). As several other studies present significantly lower annual calendar degradation values at full SOC than this value, we adjust the value by a factor of 0.25. Accordingly, a permanent 100% SOC then causes 1.96% capacity loss per year.

- In the last column, we scale the hourly values by $0.25 \times 100,000$.

Table 2. Data from [7] and processing steps

SOC	relative capacity after ten months	Q_loss 10 month period (1-rel cap)	Q_loss hourly	Q_loss entire year	Comment	Hourly value divided by 4 [10 ⁻⁵]
0.00	0.989043478	1.10%	0.000150%	1.31%	Break point 1	3.75%
4.89	0.985913043	1.41%	0.000193%	1.69%		
9.89	0.982260870	1.77%	0.000243%	2.13%		
20.02	0.979652174	2.03%	0.000279%	2.44%		
30.04	0.974434783	2.56%	0.000350%	3.07%	Break point 2	8.76%
40.05	0.974956522	2.50%	0.000343%	3.01%		
45.05	0.973913043	2.61%	0.000357%	3.13%		
50.18	0.973913043	2.61%	0.000357%	3.13%		
55.07	0.972869565	2.71%	0.000372%	3.26%		
60.07	0.970782609	2.92%	0.000400%	3.51%	Break point 3	10.01%
65.08	0.957217391	4.28%	0.000586%	5.13%		
70.08	0.946260870	5.37%	0.000736%	6.45%	Break point 4	18.40%
80.21	0.945739130	5.43%	0.000743%	6.51%		
90.23	0.944173913	5.58%	0.000765%	6.70%		
95.11	0.941043478	5.90%	0.000808%	7.07%		
100.00	0.934782609	6.52%	0.000893%	7.83%	Break point 5	22.33%

Processing steps:

- Plotted values in a graph to decide where to put the break points.

Figure 1. Plotted capacity loss values to decide where to put the Calendar aging breakpoints

Final data –Calendar aging values at breakpoints, Table 3 in the paper (Table 3 below):

Table 3. Calendar aging values at breakpoints (Table 3 in the paper.)

Break point i		1	2	3	4	5
	Scale					
o_i^{CAL}	%	0	30.036	60.072	70.083	100
y_i	10^{-7}	3.752	8.755	10.006	18.404	22.335

1.2 Electricity price (hourly)

- Source: [37] Bundesnetzagentur, Marktdaten; 2019. <https://www.smard.de/home/downloadcenter>
- Reuse permission “Die auf SMARD bereitgestellten Daten können unter der Lizenz CC BY 4.0 kostenfrei heruntergeladen, gespeichert und weiterverwendet werden.”

Following selections:

- Oberkategorie: Markt
- Datenkategorie: Großhandelspreise
- Land: Deutschland
- 22.04.2019 - 24.04.2019
- Auflösung wählen: Stunde

The downloaded file has name “Gro_handelspreise_201904220000_201904242359_Stunde.csv” – beware that the decimal point delimiter is a comma.

The first four columns are exact from the original data file. The fourth column in this file contains prices for Deutschland/Luxemburg [€/MWh] Originalauflösungen. We transform the unit, apply a network fee and Value Added Tax, and set negative and very low prices equal to 0.1.

Table 4. Hourly electricity prices, 22.04.2019 - 24.04.2019.

[37]	[37]	[37]	[37]	Scale values	+ network fee [38]	sum incl. 19% VAT [38]	"non-negative": max(price,0.1 ct)
Datum	Anfang	Ende	€/ MWh	€/ct / kWh	€/ct / kWh	€/ct / kWh	€/ct / kWh
22.04.2019	2:00	3:00	13.00	1.300	7.39	10.341	10.341
22.04.2019	3:00	4:00	10.01	1.001	7.39	9.985	9.985
22.04.2019	4:00	5:00	5.51	0.551	7.39	9.450	9.450
22.04.2019	5:00	6:00	14.82	1.482	7.39	10.558	10.558
22.04.2019	6:00	7:00	5.14	0.514	7.39	9.406	9.406
22.04.2019	7:00	8:00	3.46	0.346	7.39	9.206	9.206
22.04.2019	8:00	9:00	16.93	1.693	7.39	10.809	10.809
22.04.2019	9:00	10:00	6.45	0.645	7.39	9.562	9.562
22.04.2019	10:00	11:00	-5.26	-0.526	7.39	8.168	8.168
22.04.2019	11:00	12:00	-54.91	-5.491	7.39	2.260	2.260
22.04.2019	12:00	13:00	-62.08	-6.208	7.39	1.407	1.407
22.04.2019	13:00	14:00	-77.31	-7.731	7.39	-0.406	0.100
22.04.2019	14:00	15:00	-83.01	-8.301	7.39	-1.084	0.100
22.04.2019	15:00	16:00	-79.97	-7.997	7.39	-0.722	0.100
22.04.2019	16:00	17:00	-68.75	-6.875	7.39	0.613	0.613
22.04.2019	17:00	18:00	-43.07	-4.307	7.39	3.669	3.669
22.04.2019	18:00	19:00	-0.39	-0.039	7.39	8.748	8.748
22.04.2019	19:00	20:00	15.06	1.506	7.39	10.586	10.586
22.04.2019	20:00	21:00	17.03	1.703	7.39	10.821	10.821
22.04.2019	21:00	22:00	2.98	0.298	7.39	9.149	9.149
22.04.2019	22:00	23:00	0.03	0.003	7.39	8.798	8.798
22.04.2019	23:00	0:00	-18.85	-1.885	7.39	6.551	6.551
23.04.2019	0:00	1:00	-1.72	-0.172	7.39	8.589	8.589
23.04.2019	1:00	2:00	-6.95	-0.695	7.39	7.967	7.967
23.04.2019	2:00	3:00	-9.64	-0.964	7.39	7.647	7.647
23.04.2019	3:00	4:00	-11.03	-1.103	7.39	7.482	7.482
23.04.2019	4:00	5:00	-9.56	-0.956	7.39	7.656	7.656
23.04.2019	5:00	6:00	6.84	0.684	7.39	9.608	9.608
23.04.2019	6:00	7:00	29.45	2.945	7.39	12.299	12.299
23.04.2019	7:00	8:00	38.82	3.882	7.39	13.414	13.414
23.04.2019	8:00	9:00	38.53	3.853	7.39	13.379	13.379
23.04.2019	9:00	10:00	27.91	2.791	7.39	12.115	12.115
23.04.2019	10:00	11:00	16.47	1.647	7.39	10.754	10.754
23.04.2019	11:00	12:00	0.03	0.003	7.39	8.798	8.798
23.04.2019	12:00	13:00	-9.98	-0.998	7.39	7.606	7.606
23.04.2019	13:00	14:00	-9.97	-0.997	7.39	7.608	7.608
23.04.2019	14:00	15:00	-4.49	-0.449	7.39	8.260	8.260
23.04.2019	15:00	16:00	0.13	0.013	7.39	8.810	8.810
23.04.2019	16:00	17:00	13.08	1.308	7.39	10.351	10.351
23.04.2019	17:00	18:00	31.56	3.156	7.39	12.550	12.550
23.04.2019	18:00	19:00	38.58	3.858	7.39	13.385	13.385
23.04.2019	19:00	20:00	41.11	4.111	7.39	13.686	13.686
23.04.2019	20:00	21:00	40.68	4.068	7.39	13.635	13.635

[37]	[37]	[37]	[37]	Scale values	+ network fee [38]	sum incl. 19% VAT [38]	"non-negative": max(price,0.1 ct)
Datum	Anfang	Ende	€/ MWh	€/ct / kWh	€/ct / kWh	€/ct / kWh	€/ct / kWh
23.04.2019	21:00	22:00	36.37	3.637	7.39	13.122	13.122
23.04.2019	22:00	23:00	30.09	3.009	7.39	12.375	12.375
23.04.2019	23:00	0:00	27.72	2.772	7.39	12.093	12.093
24.04.2019	0:00	1:00	24.97	2.497	7.39	11.766	11.766
24.04.2019	1:00	2:00	24.57	2.457	7.39	11.718	11.718